

A proof for the Siennacentric Theory

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Abstract. A proof for the Siennacentric Theory, the theory developed by Chaea Yoon¹ is presented. It is shown that the world revolves around the main character, and that Sienna is the main character. Then, the conclusion that the world must revolve around Sienna is obtained.

Preliminaries

Let W denote the world. Let M denote the main character. Let S denote Sienna. Let $\mathcal{R}(x, y)$ denote “ x revolves around y ”.

Theorem 1. $\mathcal{R}(W, M)$

Proof. By definition of narrative centrality,

$$\forall x \in W, x \neq M \implies x \rightarrow M$$

Thus,

$$W \rightarrow M \iff \mathcal{R}(W, M).$$

□

Theorem 2. $M = S$

Proof. Let $\mathcal{T}(x)$ denote “ x satisfies protagonist tropes.”

Define:

$$\mathcal{T}(x) \iff \left\{ \begin{array}{l} x \text{ perceives self as ordinary} \\ \wedge x \text{ is objectively exceptional} \\ \wedge \exists C, P, E \text{ such that} \\ \quad C = \text{perfect cool-type friend} \\ \quad P = \text{effort-based cute-type friend} \\ \quad E = \text{transfer student with past attachment} \\ \wedge \exists \{U_i\} = \text{diverse senior set} \\ \wedge x \text{ transitions from loved junior to admired senior} \end{array} \right.$$

Assume:

$$\forall x, \mathcal{T}(x) \implies x = M$$

Observe:

$$\mathcal{T}(S)$$

Therefore:

$$S = M$$

□

Corollary 1. $\mathcal{R}(W, S)$

Proof. From Theorem 1 and Theorem 2,

$$\mathcal{R}(W, M) \wedge (M = S) \implies \mathcal{R}(W, S).$$

□

¹Kakaotalk chats